

BIONANOTEKNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANIB YURAK QON-TOMIR KASALLIKLARINI OLDINI OLISH USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi davrda turli yurak kasalliklari tufayli insonlarda yurak yetishmovchiligi kundan-kunga oshmoqda. Bu esa nafaqat tibbiyot balki biotexnologiya oldidagi muammolardan biridir. Hozirgi vaqtda organ transplantatsiyasi va yordamchi asboblari bu bemorlar uchun yagona samarali davolash usuli bo'lib qolmoqda. Oltin nanozarralar va uglerod nanotubalari kabi nanomateriallar yurak to'qimasini muhandislik yondashuvlari uchun foydali bo'lgan noyob xususiyatlarni taqdim etadi. Xususan, ushbu nanomateriallar to'qimalarning funktsionalligini yaxshilash uchun elektr o'tkazuvchanligini, qattiqligini modulyatsiya qilishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, ular hujayra fenotiplariga ta'sir qilish uchun bioaktiv yuklarni yetkazib berishlari mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Oltin nanozarralar, uglerod nanotubalari, nanomateriallar, elektr o'tkazuvchanlik, konyugatsiyalangan uglerod, polietilen glikol.

O'zining noyob xususiyatlari tufayli nanomateriallar yurak-qon tomir to'qimalari muhandisligida yangi imkoniyatlarni taqdim etadi. Hozirgacha nanomaterial va nanotexnologiyalar yurak-qon tomir to'qimalari muhandisligining turli sohalarida, jumladan, dori vositalarini etkazib berish, yurak mushaklari va tomir greftlarini ishlab chiqarishda keng sinovdan o'tkazilmoqda. Nanotexnologiya yurak-qon tomir regenerativ tibbiyotiga tegishli turli jihatlariga e'tibor qaratmoqda [1.2.3].

Terapevtiklar tizimli tomir ichiga yuborish orqali yuborilganda, ular qon aylanish tizimi bo'ylab o'tadi. Ushbu hodisadan foydalanib, tomir ichiga yuborish orqali yuborilgan geparin bilan konyugatsiyalangan uglerod nanokapsulalaridan foydalangan holda o'tkir orqa oyoq tromboemboliyasi sichqoncha modelida tromb shakllanishining muvaffaqiyatli oldini olishdi. Uglerodli nanokapsulalar tanlandi, chunki ular boshqa uglerod asosidagi nanomateriallarga nisbatan ko'proq biologik mos keladi va tomir ichiga yuborish uchun ko'proq mos keladi [4-7].

Geparin bilan konyugatsiyalangan uglerod nanokapsulalari faqat geparin yoki uglerod nanokapsulalariga nisbatan yaxshiroq antitrombotik faollikni namoyon etishi va trombnings hosil bo'lish vaqtini uzaytirishi ko'rsatildi. Terapevtiklar tomir ichiga yuborilgandan so'ng qon aylanish tizimi bo'ylab harakatlanar ekan, ular turli organlar tomonidan qabul qilinadi, saqlanadi va oxir-oqibat tozalanadi [8]. Funktsional bo'lmagan terapevtiklar yurakni aniq nishonga olishga qodir emas va asosan jigar va taloq kabi retikuloendotelial organlarda tugaydi. Shuning uchun, endi terapevtik vositalarni nanozarrachalar ichiga o'rash orqali "himoya qilish" yuborilmoqda [9]. Kapsulalanganidan so'ng, bu terapevtiklar tashuvchilarning fizik-kimyoviy xususiyatlariga qarab, ularning erkin shakli bilan solishtirganda ushlab turish xususiyatiga ega bo'lishi mumkin. Dori-darmonlarni nanozarrachalarda inkapsulyatsiya qilish

foydali bo'lishi mumkin, chunki u dorilarni ushlab turish va qon aylanishining faoliyatini oshirishi mumkin [10-12].

Ushbu nanozarrachalarning yuzasi, shuningdek, nanopartikullarni ma'lum saytlarga, hujayralarga yoki to'qimalarga faol yo'naltirishni ta'minlaydigan turli funktsional guruhlar bilan o'zgartirilishi mumkin. Sirtini moslashtirishning keng tarqalgan namunasi polietilen glikolning birlashtirilishidir. Faol nishonga ega bo'lmagan nanozarrachalar hali ham passiv nishonga olish orqali kasal joylariga yetib borishga qodir [13]. Kengaytirilgan o'tkazuvchanlik va ushlab turish effekti passiv nishonga olishning sababi sifatida ko'rsatilgan, buning natijasida kasal yoki shikastlangan joylarning tomirlari asta-sekin o'tkazuvchan bo'lib, dori tarkibidagi nanozarrachalar orqali o'tishiga imkon beradi. Qon tomir o'tkazuvchanligi omili ishlab chiqarilishi, shuningdek, azot oksidi, peroksinitrit va bradikinin kabi o'tkazuvchanlikni kuchaytiruvchi bir nechta birikmalar, kasallik tomirlarning o'tkazuvchanligini oshirish bilan bog'liq [14-16].

Boshqa tomondan, o'smalarda limfa tomirlarining yo'qligi va bu tomirlar orqali ekstravazatsiyaning bir tomonlama tabiati o'simta joylarida nanopartikullarni ushlab turish va to'planishning asosiy sabablari deb hisoblanadi [17].

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